

Aesthetic Rehabilitation of Congenitally Missing and Traumatically Lost Maxillary Incisors : A Case Report

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Abstract

The anterior maxillary region, often referred to as the aesthetic zone, plays a crucial role in facial harmony and function. Congenitally missing and traumatically lost maxillary incisors, particularly lateral incisors, account for approximately 20% of all dental anomalies, significantly affecting speech, appearance, and self-confidence. Advances in prosthodontic rehabilitation and an interdisciplinary treatment approach enable the effective management of such cases. By integrating patient expectations with functional and aesthetic considerations, an optimal restorative plan can be developed. This case report illustrates the successful rehabilitation of a patient with a trauma-induced central incisor loss and congenitally missing lateral incisors using a porcelain-fused-to-metal crown prosthesis, ensuring an aesthetic and functional outcome.

Keywords : Aesthetic Rehabilitation, Fixed Dental Prosthesis, Congenitally Missing Teeth, Prosthodontic Rehabilitation, Multidisciplinary Approach.

Introduction

Congenitally absent teeth are among the most common developmental dental anomalies, resulting from improper differentiation of tooth germs and leading to the absence of one or more teeth. This condition can affect both primary and permanent dentition, with significant implications for dental aesthetics and function. When one to six teeth (excluding third molars) are missing, the condition is termed hypodontia, whereas the complete absence of teeth is referred to as anodontia^[1]. The prevalence of permanent tooth agenesis varies widely across different populations and ethnic groups, with the maxillary lateral incisor being the most frequently missing anterior tooth. The congenital absence of these incisors, combined with trauma-induced loss of central incisors, presents significant challenges in restoring the aesthetics and function of the anterior maxillary region, commonly referred to as the aesthetic zone^[2].

Restoring aesthetics in the anterior maxillary region requires an interdisciplinary approach that integrates functional, cosmetic, and patient-centred considerations. Treatment planning must address factors such as occlusion, soft tissue harmony, phon-

etics, and long-term stability^[3]. The choice of restorative solutions depends on the extent of the missing teeth, available space, and overall patient expectations. Fixed prosthetic options, including conventional bridges and implant-supported restorations, offer predictable outcomes in such cases. However, managing multiple missing teeth with limited interproximal space necessitates precise space analysis, careful selection of restorative materials, and an individualized treatment approach^[4].

This case report presents the aesthetic rehabilitation of a patient with congenitally missing maxillary lateral incisors and trauma-induced loss of central incisors using a fixed dental prosthesis. Through comprehensive treatment planning and a multidisciplinary approach, an aesthetic and functionally stable outcome was achieved, effectively addressing the complexities of this case.

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Case Report

A 20-year-old female patient reported to the prosthodontics department complaining mostly of an unpleasant smile caused by lost teeth in the upper front teeth region (figure 1a). There was no significant medical history for the patient

Figure 1 : 1a. Extraoral view 1b. Intraoral view 1c. Panoramic X-ray view

The patient said that six months prior, she had fallen, resulting in the loss of her central incisor and a congenital absence of her lateral incisor. An intraoral examination identified a class I malocclusion, which included a right-side crossbite and insufficient mesiodistal width to enable the replacement of teeth 12, 11, 21, and 22 (figure 1b, 1c).

Clinical Procedure

Irreversible hydrocolloid material (Algitex DPI, India) was used to make the diagnostic impression, and a type-II gypsum product (dental plaster; Kalabhai) was used to pour the impression. Diagnostic cast mounted using a mean value articulator. A diagnostic wax-up was performed using blue inlay wax according to the Digital smile design (BEGO, Germany) (figure 4a), and a silicone index was fabricated for clinical mock-up (figure 4b). The maxillary right canine, left central incisor, and canine were prepared for PFM crowns with a shoulder finish line and subgingival margins (figure 4c). The gingival deflection was carried by a gingival retraction cord (Size #000, Sure Endo Sure Cord - Knitted Gingival Retraction Cord) (figure 4d). The final impression was made using elastomeric impression material (Neopure-Orikam Healthcare India) a two-stage putty wash technique (figure 4e) poured in Type-IV dental stone (Kalrock, Kalabhai) (figure 5a). Provisional restorations were made from a tooth-coloured acrylic resin and cemented with temporary cement (Prevest Oratemp) (figure 4f).

Figure 4: 4a. Mode wax-up 4b. Model wax-up impression taken 4c. Tooth preparation done 4d. Gingival deflection cord placed around prepared tooth 4e. Two-stage putty wash impression taken 4f. Temporary crown

The shade selection process was carried out. Wax patterns were fabricated, and then the investing, casting, and ceramic firing phases of the PFM crown were done (figure 5b,c). The final prosthesis was placed, incisal contacts were checked using articulating paper for maximum intercuspation, and any lateral interferences were adjusted using a porcelain polishing kit.

Figure 5: 5a. Working cast 5b. Wax up 5c. Final prosthesis 5d. Post-operative intraoral view

The prosthesis was then cemented using type-I glass ionomer cement (GC Gold Label 1 - Luting & Lining GIC) (figure 5d). Post-treatment instructions were provided to the patient, including the need for periodic follow-up and oral hygiene maintenance (figure 6a,b).

Figure 6: 6a. Pre-operative extra oral view 6b. Post-operative extra oral view

Discussion

The congenital absence of teeth results from environmental or genetic factors affecting dental lamina development. Hypodontia impacts both function and aesthetics, often complicating treatment. In cases of congenitally missing teeth, a vestigial ridge may develop, further challenging the restoration process. Additionally, the loss of maxillary incisors, particularly in the aesthetic zone, can significantly affect an individual's confidence and social interactions. The treatment approach depends on several factors, including the size of the edentulous space, occlusion, skeletal structure, and the condition of the remaining dentition. Other considerations include bone availability, financial feasibility, and patient preferences^[6].

Prosthetic rehabilitation offers various options based on patient needs, such as resin-bonded fixed dental prostheses, conventional fixed dental prostheses, removable partial dentures, and implant-supported restorations. Managing cases with multiple missing anterior teeth and inadequate space requires precise evaluation of occlusal harmony, facial aesthetics, and functional stability. In this case, a porcelain-fused-to-metal (PFM) fixed dental prosthesis was chosen to restore the missing maxillary incisors, ensuring a natural appearance and optimal function. The

framework was fabricated using nickel-chromium (Ni-Cr) alloy, providing strength and durability, while the veneering porcelain offered enhanced aesthetics^[7].

Following tooth preparation, the final impression was taken using the two-stage putty-wash technique with polyvinyl siloxane (PVS) impression material. This technique offers several advantages, including improved accuracy, better marginal adaptation, controlled material thickness, reduced distortion, and clinically acceptable marginal gaps (less than 120 µm)^[8]. The putty impression serves as a custom tray, ensuring uniform material thickness and detailed capture of oral structures. However, it has some limitations, such as increased chairside time, potential misalignment during the wash stage, material wastage, and the need for precise execution to avoid inaccuracies^[9].

After the impression was taken, a provisional restoration was provided using bis-acryl composite resin to protect the prepared teeth and maintain gingival health. Provisional restorations play a critical role in preventing tooth sensitivity, bacterial contamination, and space loss due to adjacent teeth drifting. Additionally, they contribute to shaping the gingival architecture, ensuring a better fit for the final prosthesis. However, provisional restorations are not as durable as permanent ones and require careful handling to avoid fractures or displacement^[10].

The final prosthesis was fabricated with a Ni-Cr metal framework and layered with feldspathic porcelain to achieve optimal aesthetics and function. Proper occlusal adjustments were made to ensure functional harmony and patient comfort. Thorough post-operative instructions were provided, and regular follow-ups were scheduled to monitor prosthesis stability and gingival health^[11].

The primary objective of treatment remains the preservation of healthy dental structures while restoring aesthetics and function. By addressing both biological and mechanical aspects, a comprehensive treatment approach can successfully rehabilitate patients with congenitally missing and traumatically lost maxillary incisors, significantly improving their quality of life^[12].

Conclusion

In prosthodontic rehabilitation, congenitally absent anterior teeth combined with anterior tooth loss present a difficult obstacle. The successful aesthetic rehabilitation of congenitally missing and traumatically lost maxillary incisors using a fixed dental prosthesis demonstrates the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration and meticulous treatment planning. Several variables, including the malocclusion, anterior relationship, necessary space, and state of the adjacent teeth, influence the clinical situation's solution. A concerted and coordinated effort that prioritizes achieving an equilibrium that minimizes the patient's concerns is necessary to achieve optimal aesthetics.

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